

PROBLEMS OF APPLYING THE OZONATION PROCESS IN GRAIN PRODUCTS AND WAYS TO SOLVE THEM

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ABSTRACT

This study analyzes the advantages and potential drawbacks of applying ozonation technology in the storage of grain and seeds, as well as in post-harvest processing. The impact of high ozone concentrations on human health, regulatory threshold limits, and safety assurance mechanisms under industrial conditions are examined. It is substantiated that environmental and technical safety can be enhanced through process automation, the use of hermetically sealed systems, and the application of catalytic decomposition methods. Furthermore, the possibility of moisture formation as a result of residual ozone decomposition is assessed, and it is determined that this factor does not have a significant effect on product quality. The research findings indicate the necessity of improving and widely implementing ozonation technology in the agro-industrial sector.

Despite the undeniable advantages of ozone treatment, this process also has certain drawbacks. The main problem associated with the use of ozone in agriculture is the potential risk posed to human health by high ozone concentrations. Therefore, ozone treatment must be carried out in hermetically sealed facilities or in environments where humans and animals are not present. According to GOST 12.1.005–88 of the Russian Federation, ozone belongs to the first hazard class of highly dangerous substances and has an acute mechanism of action.

Humans can detect the odor of ozone in air at concentrations of 0.01–0.05 mg/m³. When the concentration in an ozone–air mixture reaches 1 mg/m³, irritation of the respiratory tract is observed. In nature, ozone is formed during lightning discharges; however, its concentration does not exceed 0.1 mg/m³. This level does not harm human health and, in some cases, may even produce a slight therapeutic effect. If the ozone content in an ozone–air mixture does not exceed 0.2 mg/m³, humans and animals can remain in such an environment without harm. For this reason, many foreign countries have established 0.2 mg/m³ as the maximum permissible concentration (MPC). In Uzbekistan, this value is set at 0.1 mg/m³. The ozone concentration released into the atmosphere must not exceed 3.3 µg/m³. In populated areas, the average daily MPC in atmospheric air is 0.03 mg/m³. During ozone treatment, the maximum single concentration that does not cause harm to human health is 0.16 mg/m³.

The harmful effects of ozone on human health represent a major obstacle to the industrial implementation of this technology. In enterprises where ventilation and automation systems are insufficient, workers operating near specialized equipment may begin to experience discomfort. The first sign of ozone poisoning is the appearance of a slightly sweet taste in the mouth. If such symptoms occur, the area must be immediately evacuated and the process stopped.

This problem can be addressed by fully automating the ozone treatment process and implementing it within a closed system without direct human involvement. According to GOST 12.1.005–88, the concentration of hazardous substances with acute effects must be continuously monitored. Therefore, operator working areas should be equipped with signaling devices that indicate when the MPC is exceeded. Hazardous gas concentrations must be monitored not only inside the equipment but also in the surrounding environment.

Potential leakage points should be equipped with special catalysts capable of converting ozone into oxygen. The ozonation system should operate within a closed loop that enables the reuse of residual gas in the technological process. Autonomous equipment, alarm systems, and ozone decomposition devices ensure safe operation.

One of the most effective ways to reduce the harmful effects of high ozone concentrations is the use of well-sealed silo-type grain storage facilities. In such silos, profiled sheets are connected by bolted joints and rubber gaskets, while connection points are reinforced with additional sealing materials. For ozone treatment, silos with a conical bottom mounted on metal supports are recommended, as they allow self-unloading and eliminate areas where residual ozone could accumulate. The treated ozone–air mixture should be returned to the technological process rather than released into the atmosphere.

Loading and unloading zones must also be equipped with catalysts that prevent residual ozone from escaping into the environment. A sanitary protection zone should be established around the silo, equipped with light and sound signaling systems to indicate when MPC levels are exceeded. Small concentrations of ozone released into the atmosphere naturally decompose into oxygen. The ozonation process should be carried out in an automated mode.

Another potential drawback of using ozone technology in grain and seed storage is the formation of water molecules as a result of residual ozone decomposition. If excessive moisture forms, it may increase the moisture content of the grain mass, reduce product quality, and promote the development of fungi, bacteria, and other microorganisms.

Typically, residual O_3 decomposes into molecular oxygen (O_2) and atomic oxygen (O). Atomic oxygen is highly reactive and rapidly participates in chemical reactions, forming free radicals and initiating chain reactions that may, under certain conditions, result in the formation of water molecules (H_2O). Additionally, residual ozone may react with molecular hydrogen (H_2), forming oxygen (O_2) and water (H_2O).

However, the probability of these reactions occurring is very low; therefore, the amount of moisture formed is negligible relative to the total mass of stored grain. Consequently, ozone treatment does not significantly affect the moisture content of dry grain and seeds.

To prevent undesirable chemical reactions involving residual ozone, it is advisable to purify it before returning it to the technological process. This approach not only prevents

moisture formation but also reduces the risk of gas exposure in operator working areas, improves ozonator efficiency, and lowers the overall cost of the ozonation process.

Based on the above analysis, it is difficult to completely eliminate ozone emissions into the atmosphere; however, modern technologies make it possible to reduce ozone concentrations to safe levels. The challenges associated with the use of ozonation in post-harvest processing and storage are not sufficient grounds to abandon this environmentally friendly technology. On the contrary, improving ozonation systems, developing the necessary technical equipment, and systematically implementing ozone treatment of grain mass within the agro-industrial complex represent a relevant and перспективе направление

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